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FjordPhantom Malware Process and Execution Analysis in Mobile Banking Application

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Technological development and acceleration cannot be avoided in the digital era. Technology is used in various transactions to support existing productivity. But behind it all, some vulnerabilities and risks always arise without users realizing it. One of them is FjordPhantom. Fjordphantom is the name of malware with different characteristics from most malware. *This malware is a combination of malware attacks on various banking service applications. The process carried out by the creator of this malware is to embed the software into the virtualization server where the official banking service application is located. The impact is extraordinary and causes the users or customers served to lose quite a lot of material.* This research was conducted to provide an overview of this malware in the real world. The author tries to study this by analyzing various information obtained from journals and papers related to the process and execution carried out by the malware on existing banking service applications. *The research method used is qualitative, with a research model, namely, a systematic literature review. Based on the analysis results and conclusions obtained, 22 papers discussed this malware.*

In contrast, *until now, most existing banking service technology application users have still not been aware of this malware.* The author's hope in writing about the process and execution carried out by this malware is to provide an accurate picture that behind the technology used and used as a reference by its users, it is necessary always to be aware of it and make important notes in its use. And in the future, other malware that is more sophisticated in technology may emerge.

- ✓ Malware, short for malicious software, is designed to harm or disrupt computer systems. It can be categorized by its ability to replicate, propagate, self-execute, and cause damage
- ✓ FjordPhantom is an Android malware targeting banking apps to steal user data. It spreads via SMS, email, and messaging apps, using virtualization to run within virtual containers, making it harder for security systems to detect
- ✓ Cybercrime encompasses all criminal activities involving the internet or computers, such as fraud, theft, and data manipulation. It evolves from the misuse of applications or internet services and continues to grow with increased internet penetration.

- How does the FjordPhantom malware execute its attacks on mobile banking apps, and what is the process?

Fig .1 Research Steps
Source : Author

Table 1 : The Paper Resources

Year	Journal	Conference	Webpage	Total (%)
2009	[7]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2012	[9]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2013	-	[10],[11]	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2014	[2]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2015	[16],[20]	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2016	[12]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2017	[3]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2018	[21]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2019	[22]	-	-	1 Publication (4.54%)
2020	[1],[8]	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2021	-	-	[6]	1 Publication (4.54%)
2022	[14], [15]	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2023	[4],[13],	-	-	2 Publication (9.09%)
2024	[5]	-	[17],[18], [19]	4 Publication (18.18%)
Total	16 Publication (72.72%)	2 Publication (9.09%)	4 Publication (18.18%)	22 Publication (100%)

Table 2 : Fjordphantom

How FjordPhantom works

Conclusion

- FjordPhantom is a malware that attack banking applications and can only be found in Android operating system.
- The findings from this research is FjordPhantom malware uses virtualization techniques, that allowing the malware to steal data without the knowledge of the user.
- The reason it can only be found in Android operating system is because Android is an open-source operating system

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